

Evapotranspiration, Dependable Discharge and flow duration curve of Inggemun River

Rainfaal (R)

No	Year	Month											
		Jan	Feb	Marc	Apr	may	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nop	Dec
1	2012	202.74	256.09	441	184.32	447.31	333.74	153.51	157.24	163.22	100.98	231.27	183.62
2	2013	452.35	487.35	428.65	319.56	175.63	153.37	245.69	308.03	119.67	142.76	245.76	270.61
3	2014	311.37	123.95	436.04	305.52	276.33	128.32	243.95	213.32	224.61	71.29	182.62	343.55
4	2015	209.09	412.57	444.3	614.69	195.09	209.45	55.98	52.99	49.8	64.64	85.58	591.47
5	2016	437.9	366.18	342.92	444.45	221.11	213.55	447.11	152.06	186.24	167.5	210.89	292.05
6	2017	251.74	393.38	426.85	592.95	264.93	254.46	308.67	190.2	217.15	220.37	187.99	291.17
7	2018	214.1	382.25	456.05	226.92	140.55	151.1	213.48	104.24	112.87	137.56	375.66	371.93
8	2019	485.3	478.5	331.68	361.53	265.48	299.63	145.1	108.68	73.16	126.52	88.87	279.18
9	2020	166.98	605.03	490.42	625.8	133.41	127.89	150.54	139.1	90.55	152.89	356.31	379.49
10	2021	137.98	494.82	214.95	477.86	334.91	167.8	206.95	268.38	241.74	97.75	117.73	378.4
	Total	2869.55	4000.12	4012.86	4153.6	2454.75	2039.31	2170.98	1694.24	1479.01	1282.26	2082.68	3381.47
	Average	286.955	400.012	401.286	415.36	245.475	203.931	217.098	169.424	147.901	128.226	208.268	338.147

Number of day rain (n)

No	Year	Month											
		Jan	Feb	Marc	Apr	may	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nop	Dec
1	2012	16	15	20	14	24	19	10	9	12	7	11	10
2	2013	15	14	18	16	12	11	17	14	3	8	12	17
3	2014	14	6	16	16	17	11	7	13	13	6	11	13
4	2015	15	18	19	24	11	12	2	2	3	4	6	21
5	2016	18	17	18	18	8	12	21	10	10	12	14	19
6	2017	18	22	21	24	16	14	14	12	13	8	10	16
7	2018	13	23	17	15	12	11	9	8	7	9	17	18

8	2019	23	17	17	13	16	16	11	7	4	11	7	11
9	2020	8	17	21	20	7	10	13	10	5	9	18	15
10	2021	11	18	14	20	18	15	12	15	13	10	7	20
	Total	151	167	181	180	141	131	116	100	83	84	113	160

Suhu/temperatur (oC)

Year	Month											
	Jan	Feb	Marc	Apr	may	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nop	Dec
2012	21.9	21.72	21.7	21.89	21.86	21.26	21.17	21.27	21.44	21.99	22.1	22.27
2013	22.1	22.18	22.4	22.12	22.29	22.04	21.44	21.18	21.7	21.54	21.83	22.12
2014	21.71	21.9	22.19	22.19	22.38	22.07	21.48	21.37	21.3	22.18	22.28	22.14
2015	21.97	21.74	22.18	22.26	22.13	21.65	21.27	21.43	21.79	22.23	22.33	22.67
2016	22.63	22.68	22.86	22.97	22.85	22.14	21.76	21.85	21.83	21.99	22.45	22.07
2017	22.1	21.84	21.88	22.13	22.45	21.57	21.23	21.69	21.92	22.37	22.39	22.23
2018	22.08	21.96	22.03	22.23	22.48	21.55	21.69	21.3	21.5	21.97	22.37	22.37
2019	22.21	22.27	22.15	22.62	22.6	22.12	21.32	21.48	21.68	22.1	22.25	22.6
2020	22.83	22.87	22.47	22.48	22.76	22.13	21.74	21.81	22.12	22.01	22.21	22.11
2021	22.25	21.79	22.03	21.88	22.41	21.69	21.8	21.8	21.88	22.3	22.25	22.08
Total	221.78	220.95	221.89	222.77	224.21	218.22	214.9	215.18	217.16	220.68	222.46	222.66
Maks	22.83	22.87	22.86	22.97	22.85	22.14	21.8	21.85	22.12	22.37	22.45	22.67
Min	21.71	21.72	21.7	21.88	21.86	21.26	21.17	21.18	21.3	21.54	21.83	22.07

Humidity (%)

No	Year	Month											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	2012	90.62	89.81	90.94	91.06	92.88	93.19	91.69	91.38	91.12	89.69	91.56	91.62
2	2013	91.19	90.69	90.56	92.19	91.38	92.25	93	91.44	90.62	90.44	91.94	92.38
3	2014	90.12	88.75	90.81	91.56	91.62	91.88	91.44	91.69	90.56	88.62	90.25	92.62
4	2015	90.88	90.56	90.75	91.81	91.69	92.06	89.81	88.44	88.31	86.94	91	90.75
5	2016	92.69	91.56	92.38	92.06	92	92.88	93.12	90.5	91.19	91.69	91.19	91.81
6	2017	91.56	91.06	91.38	92.06	92.44	92.5	92.12	91	90.31	90.12	92.19	91.19
7	2018	91.5	90.88	90.44	91.31	90.75	90.5	92.25	90.56	90.44	90.25	90.69	91.5
8	2019	91.44	91.62	90.56	91.56	92.38	92.31	91.69	90.56	88.94	90.19	89.25	90.38
9	2020	89.88	90.38	91.75	91.81	91.12	91.12	89.88	90.31	89.5	89.81	91.38	91.88
10	2021	91.56	90.75	90.81	91.31	92.12	91.94	91.62	91.25	90.88	91	90.44	91.44
	Total	911.44	906.06	910.38	916.73	918.38	920.63	916.62	907.13	901.87	898.75	909.89	915.57
	Maks	92.69	91.62	92.38	92.19	92.88	93.19	93.12	91.69	91.19	91.69	92.19	92.62
	Min	89.88	88.75	90.44	91.06	90.75	90.5	89.81	88.44	88.31	86.94	89.25	90.38
	Average	91.144	90.606	91.038	91.673	91.838	92.063	91.662	90.713	90.187	89.875	90.989	91.557

Wind speed (m/dtk)

No	year	Month											
		Jan	Feb	Marc	Apr	may	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nop	Dec
1	2012	0.82	0.89	0.93	0.75	0.79	0.87	0.98	0.77	0.91	0.94	0.67	0.7
2	2013	0.8	0.73	0.69	0.8	0.89	0.64	0.89	0.96	0.91	0.93	0.82	0.66
3	2014	0.98	0.83	0.7	0.86	0.72	0.81	0.86	0.88	0.86	0.88	0.81	0.66
4	2015	0.79	0.75	0.71	0.69	0.84	1.01	0.95	0.9	0.86	0.98	0.71	0.59
5	2016	0.58	0.64	0.55	0.55	0.78	0.67	0.81	0.92	0.86	0.8	0.72	0.8
6	2017	0.77	0.83	0.72	0.74	0.71	0.92	0.88	0.87	0.88	0.81	0.66	0.86
7	2018	0.74	0.81	0.95	0.82	0.84	0.93	0.77	0.81	0.91	0.91	0.82	0.89
8	2019	0.82	0.68	0.75	0.73	0.7	0.92	0.89	0.94	0.94	0.73	0.88	0.78
9	2020	0.73	0.62	0.67	0.63	0.93	0.89	0.96	0.88	0.9	0.88	0.92	0.7
10	2021	0.74	0.9	0.62	0.91	0.98	0.9	0.83	0.9	0.89	0.84	0.94	0.95
	Total	7.77	7.68	7.29	7.48	8.18	8.56	8.82	8.83	8.92	8.7	7.95	7.59
	Maks	0.98	0.9	0.95	0.91	0.98	1.01	0.98	0.96	0.94	0.98	0.94	0.95
	Min	0.58	0.62	0.55	0.55	0.7	0.64	0.77	0.77	0.86	0.73	0.66	0.59
	Average	0.777	0.768	0.729	0.748	0.818	0.856	0.882	0.883	0.892	0.87	0.795	0.759

Radiation (%)

No	Year	Month											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	2012	48	48	44	48	52	45	42	41	46	51	45	48
2	2013	47	46	52	48	48	47	43	43	45	46	45	47
3	2014	48	51	50	52	53	47	47	43	45	51	46	46
4	2015	50	50	50	54	52	49	52	47	52	54	46	54
5	2016	48	50	45	52	52	48	45	50	45	44	48	48
6	2017	48	47	47	48	49	45	43	41	44	49	47	48
7	2018	48	46	51	49	52	46	46	45	46	45	47	50
8	2019	52	48	55	48	50	41	43	41	46	47	54	52
9	2020	55	53	51	54	51	48	46	45	45	47	48	48
10	2021	46	45	48	48	50	47	46	47	43	48	48	45

	Total	490	484	493	501	509	463	453	443	457	482	474	486
	Maks	55	53	55	54	53	49	52	50	52	54	54	54
	Min	46	45	44	48	48	41	42	41	43	44	45	45
	Average	49	48.4	49.3	50.1	50.9	46.3	45.3	44.3	45.7	48.2	47.4	48.6

Et0 Inggemum River 2012															
No.	Varibale	Unit	Expl	Evapotranspiration 2012											
				Jan	Feb	Marc	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Des
1	Temperature (T)	oC	Data	21.900	21.720	21.700	21.890	21.860	21.260	21.170	21.270	21.440	21.990	22.100	22.270
2	Ea (ea)	mbar	Table	26.250	25.980	25.950	26.235	26.190	25.290	25.155	25.305	25.560	26.385	26.550	26.859
3	W		Table	0.711	0.710	0.709	0.711	0.711	0.705	0.704	0.705	0.707	0.712	0.713	0.715
4	1-W		Cal	0.289	0.291	0.291	0.289	0.289	0.295	0.296	0.295	0.293	0.288	0.287	0.285
5	f(T)		Table	14.980	14.944	14.940	14.978	14.972	14.852	14.834	14.854	14.888	14.998	15.020	15.054
6	Humidity (RH)	%	Data	90.620	89.810	90.940	91.060	92.880	93.190	91.690	91.380	91.120	89.690	91.560	91.620
7	Ed = ea x RH		Cal	23.788	23.333	23.599	23.890	24.325	23.568	23.065	23.124	23.290	23.665	24.309	24.608
8	ed = ea - Ed		Cal	2.462	2.647	2.351	2.345	1.865	1.722	2.090	2.181	2.270	2.720	2.241	2.251
9	Square		Cal	1.569	1.627	1.533	1.531	1.366	1.312	1.446	1.477	1.507	1.649	1.497	1.500
10	F(ed) = 0.34 - 0.044 squaed		Cal	0.271	0.268	0.273	0.273	0.280	0.282	0.276	0.275	0.274	0.267	0.274	0.274
12	Ra	mm/day	Table	15.150	15.600	15.700	15.200	14.250	13.700	13.900	14.650	15.250	15.450	15.200	14.950
13	Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.480	0.480	0.440	0.480	0.520	0.450	0.420	0.410	0.460	0.510	0.450	0.480
14	Rs=(0.25+0.54 n/N).Ra		Cal	7.714	7.944	7.655	7.740	7.564	6.754	6.628	6.906	7.601	8.117	7.494	7.613
15	Rns = (1-a)Rs, a=0.25		Cal	5.786	5.958	5.741	5.805	5.673	5.066	4.971	5.180	5.700	6.088	5.620	5.709
16	F(n/N) = 0.1+0.9 n/N	%	Cal	0.532	0.532	0.496	0.532	0.568	0.505	0.478	0.469	0.514	0.559	0.505	0.532
17	Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.820	0.890	0.930	0.750	0.790	0.870	0.980	0.770	0.910	0.940	0.670	0.700
18	F(u) = 0.27(1+(u/0.864))		Cal	0.461	0.478	0.487	0.445	0.454	0.473	0.499	0.450	0.482	0.489	0.426	0.433
19	Rn1=f(t).f(ed).f(n/N)		Cal	2.159	2.134	2.020	2.172	2.380	2.117	1.960	1.916	2.095	2.242	2.079	2.194

20	$R_n = R_{ns} - R_{n1}$	mm/day	Cal	3.626	3.824	3.722	3.633	3.292	2.949	3.011	3.264	3.606	3.846	3.541	3.515
21	Correction figure (c)		Data	1.100	1.100	1.000	1.000	0.950	0.950	1.000	1.000	1.100	1.100	1.150	1.150
22	Eto*	mm/day	Cal	2.907	3.080	2.973	2.885	2.586	2.319	2.428	2.590	2.869	3.122	2.800	2.791
23	$E_{t0} = c \times E_{to}^*$	mm/day	Cal	3.198	3.388	2.973	2.885	2.456	2.203	2.428	2.590	3.156	3.434	3.220	3.210
24	Number of days in one month	Day	Cal	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
25	Eto	mm/Month	Cal	99.142	94.872	92.156	86.547	76.144	66.086	75.274	80.295	94.688	106.466	96.585	99.508

Varibale	Unit	exp	Evapotranspiration 2013											
			JAN	FEB	Maret	APR	MEI	JUN	JUL	AGU	SEP	OKT	NOV	DES
Temperature (T)	oC	Data	22.100	22.180	22.400	22.120	22.290	22.040	21.440	21.180	21.700	21.540	21.830	22.120
Ea (ea)	mbar	Tabel	26.570	26.706	27.080	26.604	26.893	26.468	25.560	25.170	25.950	25.710	26.111	26.604
W		Tabel	0.713	0.714	0.716	0.714	0.715	0.713	0.707	0.704	0.709	0.708	0.711	0.714
1-W		Hitungan	0.287	0.286	0.284	0.287	0.285	0.287	0.293	0.296	0.291	0.292	0.289	0.287
f(T)		Tabel	15.020	15.036	15.080	15.024	15.058	15.008	14.888	14.836	14.940	14.908	14.966	15.024
Humidity (RH)	%	Data	91.190	90.690	90.560	92.190	91.380	92.250	93.000	91.440	90.620	90.440	91.940	92.380
Ed = ea x RH		Hitungan	24.229	24.220	24.524	24.526	24.575	24.417	23.771	23.015	23.516	23.252	24.006	24.577
ed = ea - Ed		Hitungan	2.341	2.486	2.556	2.078	2.318	2.051	1.789	2.155	2.434	2.458	2.105	2.027
Square		Hitungan	1.530	1.577	1.599	1.441	1.523	1.432	1.338	1.468	1.560	1.568	1.451	1.424
$F(ed) = 0.34 - 0.044 \text{ sqaue ed}$		Hitungan	0.273	0.271	0.270	0.277	0.273	0.277	0.281	0.275	0.271	0.271	0.276	0.277
Ra	mm/day	Tabel	15.150	15.600	15.700	15.200	14.250	13.700	13.900	14.650	15.250	15.450	15.200	14.950
Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.470	0.460	0.520	0.480	0.480	0.470	0.430	0.430	0.450	0.460	0.450	0.470
$R_s = (0.25 + 0.54 \text{ n/N}) \cdot R_a$		Hitungan	7.633	7.775	8.334	7.740	7.256	6.902	6.703	7.064	7.518	7.700	7.494	7.532
$R_{ns} = (1-a)R_s, a=0.25$		Hitungan	5.724	5.831	6.250	5.805	5.442	5.177	5.027	5.298	5.639	5.775	5.620	5.649
$F(n/N) = 0.1 + 0.9 \text{ n/N}$	%	Hitungan	0.523	0.514	0.568	0.532	0.532	0.523	0.487	0.487	0.505	0.514	0.505	0.523
Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.800	0.730	0.690	0.800	0.890	0.640	0.890	0.960	0.910	0.930	0.820	0.660
$F(u) = 0.27(1 + (u \times 0.864))$		Hitungan	0.457	0.440	0.431	0.457	0.478	0.419	0.478	0.494	0.482	0.487	0.461	0.424
$R_{n1} = f(t) \cdot f(ed) \cdot f(n/N)$		Hitungan	2.142	2.091	2.310	2.211	2.187	2.174	2.038	1.990	2.047	2.077	2.087	2.179
$R_n = R_{ns} - R_{n1}$	mm/day	Hitungan	3.582	3.740	3.940	3.594	3.255	3.002	2.989	3.308	3.591	3.698	3.533	3.470
Correction figure (c)		Data	1.100	1.100	1.000	1.000	0.950	0.950	1.000	1.000	1.100	1.100	1.150	1.150

Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	2.862	2.984	3.135	2.836	2.643	2.387	2.363	2.644	2.889	2.967	2.791	2.722
Et0 = c x Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	3.148	3.282	3.135	2.836	2.511	2.268	2.363	2.644	3.178	3.264	3.210	3.130
Number of days in one month	Day	Hitungan	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Eto	mm/bulan	Hitungan	97.586	91.894	97.189	85.090	77.846	68.028	73.241	81.972	95.325	101.183	96.306	97.031

Varibale	Unit	exp	Evapotranspiration 2015											
			JAN	FEB	Maret	APR	MEI	JUN	JUL	AGU	SEP	OKT	NOV	DES
Temperature (T)	oC	Data	21.71	21.9	22.19	22.19	22.38	22.07	21.48	21.37	21.3	22.18	22.28	22.14
Ea (ea)	mbar	Tabel	25.965	26.25	26.723	26.723	27.046	26.519	25.62	25.455	25.35	26.67	26.876	26.638
W		Tabel	0.709	0.709	0.714	0.714	0.716	0.713	0.709	0.709	0.709	0.714	0.715	0.714
1-W		Hitungan	0.2906	0.2906	0.2858	0.2858	0.2839	0.287	0.2906	0.2906	0.2906	0.2859	0.2849	0.2863
f(T)		Tabel	14.94	14.94	15.04	15.04	15.08	15.01	14.94	14.94	14.94	15.04	15.06	15.03
Humidity (RH)	%	Data	90.12	88.75	90.81	91.56	91.62	91.88	91.44	91.69	90.56	88.62	90.25	92.62
Ed = ea x RH		Hitungan	23.39966	23.29688	24.26716	24.46758	24.77955	24.36566	23.42693	23.33969	22.95696	23.63495	24.25559	24.67212
ed = ea - Ed		Hitungan	2.565342	2.953125	2.455844	2.255421	2.266455	2.153343	2.193072	2.115311	2.39304	3.035046	2.62041	1.965884
Square		Hitungan	1.601669	1.718466	1.567113	1.501806	1.505475	1.467427	1.480902	1.454411	1.546945	1.742138	1.618768	1.4021
F(ed) = 0.34 - 0.044 square ed		Hitungan	0.269527	0.264388	0.271047	0.273921	0.273759	0.275433	0.27484	0.276006	0.271934	0.263346	0.268774	0.278308
Ra	mm/day	Tabel	15.15	15.6	15.7	15.2	14.25	13.7	13.9	14.65	15.25	15.45	15.2	14.95
Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.48	0.51	0.5	0.52	0.53	0.47	0.47	0.43	0.45	0.51	0.46	0.46
Rs=(0.25+0.54 n/N).Ra		Hitungan	7.71438	8.19624	8.164	8.06816	7.64085	6.90206	7.00282	7.06423	7.51825	8.11743	7.57568	7.45108
Rns = (1-a)Rs, a=0.25		Hitungan	5.785785	6.14718	6.123	6.05112	5.730638	5.176545	5.252115	5.298173	5.638688	6.088073	5.68176	5.58831
F(n/N) = 0.1+0.9 n/N	%	Hitungan	0.532	0.559	0.55	0.568	0.577	0.523	0.523	0.487	0.505	0.559	0.514	0.514
Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.98	0.83	0.7	0.86	0.72	0.81	0.86	0.88	0.86	0.88	0.81	0.66
F(u) = 0.27(1+(ux0.864)		Hitungan	0.498614	0.463622	0.433296	0.470621	0.437962	0.458957	0.470621	0.475286	0.470621	0.475286	0.458957	0.423965
Rn1=f(t).f(ed).f(n/N)		Hitungan	2.142506	2.208317	2.241803	2.339715	2.38139	2.16279	2.147785	2.008427	2.051938	2.213455	2.079986	2.149757
Rn = Rns - Rn1	mm/day	Hitungan	3.643279	3.938863	3.881197	3.711405	3.349248	3.013755	3.10433	3.289745	3.586749	3.874617	3.601774	3.438553
Correction figure (c)		Data	1.10	1.10	1.00	1.00	0.95	0.95	1.00	1.00	1.10	1.10	1.15	1.15
Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	2.956254	3.1921	3.076073	2.954047	2.680201	2.432447	2.502141	2.625908	2.871718	3.17928	2.918265	2.692717
Et0 = c x Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	3.251879	3.51131	3.076073	2.954047	2.546191	2.310824	2.502141	2.625908	3.15889	3.497208	3.356005	3.096624

Number of days in one month	Day	Hitungan	31	28	31	30	31	30	31	31	30	31	30	31
Eto	mm/bulan	Hitungan	100.8082	98.31668	95.35826	88.62141	78.93192	69.32473	77.56638	81.40315	94.76669	108.4134	100.6802	95.99534

Varibale	Unit	exp	Evapotranspiration 2015											
			JAN	FEB	Maret	APR	MEI	JUN	JUL	AGU	SEP	OKT	NOV	DES
Temperature (T)	oC	Data	21.970	21.740	22.180	22.260	22.130	21.650	21.270	21.430	21.790	22.230	22.330	22.670
Ea (ea)	mbar	Tabel	26.355	26.010	26.706	26.842	26.621	25.805	25.305	25.545	26.085	26.745	26.961	27.539
W		Tabel	0.712	0.710	0.714	0.715	0.714	0.709	0.705	0.707	0.710	0.715	0.716	0.719
1-W		Hitungan	0.288	0.290	0.286	0.285	0.286	0.291	0.295	0.293	0.290	0.285	0.284	0.281
f(T)		Tabel	14.994	14.948	15.036	15.052	15.026	14.930	14.854	14.886	14.958	15.046	15.066	15.134
Humidity (RH)	%	Data	90.880	90.560	90.750	91.810	91.690	92.060	89.810	88.440	88.310	86.940	91.000	90.750
Ed = ea x RH		Hitungan	23.951	23.555	24.236	24.644	24.409	23.756	22.726	22.592	23.036	23.252	24.535	24.992
ed = ea - Ed		Hitungan	2.404	2.455	2.470	2.198	2.212	2.049	2.579	2.953	3.049	3.493	2.426	2.547
Square		Hitungan	1.550	1.567	1.572	1.483	1.487	1.431	1.606	1.718	1.746	1.869	1.558	1.596
F(ed) = 0.34 - 0.044 square ed		Hitungan	0.272	0.271	0.271	0.275	0.275	0.277	0.269	0.264	0.263	0.258	0.271	0.270
Ra	mm/day	Tabel	15.150	15.600	15.700	15.200	14.250	13.700	13.900	14.650	15.250	15.450	15.200	14.950
Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.500	0.500	0.500	0.540	0.520	0.490	0.520	0.470	0.520	0.540	0.460	0.540
Rs=(0.25+0.54 n/N).Ra		Hitungan	7.878	8.112	8.164	8.232	7.564	7.050	7.378	7.381	8.095	8.368	7.576	8.097
Rns = (1-a)Rs, a=0.25		Hitungan	5.909	6.084	6.123	6.174	5.673	5.288	5.534	5.536	6.071	6.276	5.682	6.073
F(n/N) = 0.1+0.9 n/N	%	Hitungan	0.550	0.550	0.550	0.586	0.568	0.541	0.568	0.523	0.568	0.586	0.514	0.586
Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.790	0.750	0.710	0.690	0.840	1.010	0.950	0.900	0.860	0.980	0.710	0.590
F(u) = 0.27(1+(ux0.864)		Hitungan	0.454	0.445	0.436	0.431	0.466	0.506	0.492	0.480	0.471	0.499	0.436	0.408
Rn1=f(t).f(ed).f(n/N)		Hitungan	2.241	2.228	2.240	2.424	2.343	2.238	2.272	2.058	2.236	2.273	2.102	2.392
Rn = Rns - Rn1	mm/day	Hitungan	3.667	3.856	3.883	3.751	3.330	3.050	3.261	3.477	3.835	4.003	3.580	3.680
Correction figure (c)		Data	1.100	1.100	1.000	1.000	0.950	0.950	1.000	1.000	1.100	1.100	1.150	1.150
Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	2.926	3.053	3.081	2.951	2.671	2.464	2.673	2.873	3.140	3.358	2.862	2.938
Et0 = c x Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	3.218	3.359	3.081	2.951	2.538	2.340	2.673	2.873	3.454	3.693	3.292	3.379
Number of days in one month	Day	Hitungan	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Eto	mm/bulan	Hitungan	99.760	94.046	95.500	88.545	78.668	70.210	82.864	89.056	103.607	114.496	98.745	104.734

Varibale	Unit	exp	Evapotranspiration 2016											
			JAN	FEB	Maret	APR	MEI	JUN	JUL	AGU	SEP	OKT	NOV	DES
Temperature (T)	oC	Data	22.630	22.680	22.860	22.970	22.850	22.140	21.760	21.850	21.830	21.990	22.450	22.070
Ea (ea)	mbar	Tabel	27.471	27.556	27.862	28.049	27.845	26.638	26.040	26.175	26.145	26.385	27.165	26.519
W		Tabel	0.719	0.719	0.721	0.722	0.721	0.714	0.710	0.711	0.711	0.712	0.717	0.713
1-W		Hitungan	0.281	0.281	0.279	0.278	0.279	0.286	0.290	0.289	0.289	0.288	0.283	0.287
f(T)		Tabel	15.126	15.136	15.172	15.194	15.170	15.028	14.952	14.970	14.966	14.998	15.090	15.014
Humidity (RH)	%	Data	92.690	91.560	92.380	92.060	92.000	92.880	93.120	90.500	91.190	91.690	91.190	91.810
Ed = ea x RH		Hitungan	25.463	25.230	25.739	25.822	25.617	24.741	24.248	23.688	23.842	24.192	24.772	24.347
ed = ea - Ed		Hitungan	2.008	2.326	2.123	2.227	2.228	1.897	1.792	2.487	2.303	2.193	2.393	2.172
Square		Hitungan	1.417	1.525	1.457	1.492	1.493	1.377	1.338	1.577	1.518	1.481	1.547	1.474
F(ed) = 0.34 - 0.044 sqaue ed		Hitungan	0.278	0.273	0.276	0.274	0.274	0.279	0.281	0.271	0.273	0.275	0.272	0.275
Ra	mm/day	Tabel	15.150	15.600	15.700	15.200	14.250	13.700	13.900	14.650	15.250	15.450	15.200	14.950
Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.480	0.500	0.450	0.520	0.520	0.480	0.450	0.500	0.450	0.440	0.480	0.480
Rs=(0.25+0.54 n/N).Ra		Hitungan	7.714	8.112	7.740	8.068	7.564	6.976	6.853	7.618	7.518	7.533	7.740	7.613
Rns = (1-a)Rs, a=0.25		Hitungan	5.786	6.084	5.805	6.051	5.673	5.232	5.140	5.714	5.639	5.650	5.805	5.709
F(n/N) = 0.1+0.9 n/N	%	Hitungan	0.532	0.550	0.505	0.568	0.568	0.532	0.505	0.550	0.505	0.496	0.532	0.532
Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.580	0.640	0.550	0.550	0.780	0.670	0.810	0.920	0.860	0.800	0.720	0.800
F(u) = 0.27(1+(ux0.864)		Hitungan	0.405	0.419	0.398	0.398	0.452	0.426	0.459	0.485	0.471	0.457	0.438	0.457
Rn1=f(t).f(ed).f(n/N)		Hitungan	2.234	2.272	2.114	2.368	2.364	2.234	2.123	2.228	2.065	2.045	2.183	2.198
Rn = Rns - Rn1	mm/day	Hitungan	3.552	3.812	3.691	3.684	3.309	2.998	3.017	3.485	3.574	3.605	3.622	3.512
Correction figure (c)		Data	1.100	1.100	1.000	1.000	0.950	0.950	1.000	1.000	1.100	1.100	1.150	1.150
Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	2.781	3.015	2.897	2.906	2.666	2.371	2.380	2.826	2.853	2.856	2.893	2.788
Et0 = c x Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	3.059	3.317	2.897	2.906	2.533	2.253	2.380	2.826	3.139	3.142	3.327	3.207
Number of days in one month	Day	Hitungan	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Eto	mm/bulan	Hitungan	94.838	92.870	89.808	87.184	78.523	67.582	73.788	87.603	94.156	97.388	99.808	99.407

Varibale	Unit	exp	Evapotranspiration 2017											
			JAN	FEB	Maret	APR	MEI	JUN	JUL	AGU	SEP	OKT	NOV	DES
Temperature (T)	oC	Data	22.100	21.840	21.880	22.130	22.450	21.570	21.230	21.690	21.920	22.370	22.390	22.230

Ea (ea)	mbar	Tabel	26.570	26.160	26.220	26.621	27.165	25.755	25.245	25.935	26.280	27.029	27.063	26.791
W		Tabel	0.713	0.711	0.711	0.714	0.717	0.708	0.705	0.709	0.712	0.716	0.716	0.715
1-W		Hitungan	0.287	0.289	0.289	0.286	0.283	0.292	0.295	0.291	0.289	0.284	0.284	0.285
f(T)		Tabel	15.020	14.968	14.976	15.026	15.090	14.914	14.846	14.938	14.984	15.074	15.078	15.046
Humidity (RH)	%	Data	91.560	91.060	91.380	92.060	92.440	92.500	92.120	91.000	90.310	90.120	92.190	91.190
Ed = ea x RH		Hitungan	24.327	23.821	23.960	24.507	25.111	23.823	23.256	23.601	23.733	24.359	24.949	24.431
ed = ea - Ed		Hitungan	2.243	2.339	2.260	2.114	2.054	1.932	1.989	2.334	2.547	2.670	2.114	2.360
Square		Hitungan	1.498	1.529	1.503	1.454	1.433	1.390	1.410	1.528	1.596	1.634	1.454	1.536
F(ed) = 0.34 - 0.044 square ed		Hitungan	0.274	0.273	0.274	0.276	0.277	0.279	0.278	0.273	0.270	0.268	0.276	0.272
Ra	mm/day	Tabel	15.150	15.600	15.700	15.200	14.250	13.700	13.900	14.650	15.250	15.450	15.200	14.950
Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.480	0.470	0.470	0.480	0.490	0.450	0.430	0.410	0.440	0.490	0.470	0.480
Rs=(0.25+0.54 n/N).Ra		Hitungan	7.714	7.859	7.910	7.740	7.333	6.754	6.703	6.906	7.436	7.951	7.658	7.613
Rns = (1-a)Rs, a=0.25		Hitungan	5.786	5.894	5.932	5.805	5.500	5.066	5.027	5.180	5.577	5.963	5.743	5.709
F(n/N) = 0.1+0.9 n/N	%	Hitungan	0.532	0.523	0.523	0.532	0.541	0.505	0.487	0.469	0.496	0.541	0.523	0.532
Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.770	0.830	0.720	0.740	0.710	0.920	0.880	0.870	0.880	0.810	0.660	0.860
F(u) = 0.27(1+(u ^{0.864}))		Hitungan	0.450	0.464	0.438	0.443	0.436	0.485	0.475	0.473	0.475	0.459	0.424	0.471
Rn1=f(t).f(ed).f(n/N)		Hitungan	2.190	2.135	2.145	2.207	2.261	2.100	2.010	1.911	2.005	2.186	2.177	2.180
Rn = Rns - Rn1	mm/day	Hitungan	3.595	3.760	3.787	3.598	3.239	2.965	3.017	3.268	3.572	3.777	3.567	3.529
Correction figure (c)		Data	1.100	1.100	1.000	1.000	0.950	0.950	1.000	1.000	1.100	1.100	1.150	1.150
Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	2.854	2.986	2.979	2.836	2.575	2.373	2.405	2.639	2.891	3.052	2.809	2.839
Et0 = c x Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	3.139	3.284	2.979	2.836	2.446	2.254	2.405	2.639	3.180	3.357	3.230	3.265
Number of days in one month	Day	Hitungan	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Eto	mm/bulan	Hitungan	97.312	91.957	92.353	85.072	75.834	67.626	74.567	81.809	95.389	104.077	96.900	101.204

Varibale	Unit	exp	Evapotranspiration 2018											
			JAN	FEB	Maret	APR	MEI	JUN	JUL	AGU	SEP	OKT	NOV	DES
Temperature (T)	oC	Data	22.080	21.960	22.030	22.230	22.480	21.550	21.690	21.300	21.500	21.970	22.370	22.370
Ea (ea)	mbar	Tabel	26.536	26.340	26.451	26.791	27.216	25.725	25.935	25.350	25.650	26.355	27.029	27.029
W		Tabel	0.713	0.712	0.713	0.715	0.717	0.708	0.709	0.705	0.707	0.712	0.716	0.716
1-W		Hitungan	0.287	0.288	0.287	0.285	0.283	0.292	0.291	0.295	0.293	0.288	0.284	0.284
f(T)		Tabel	15.016	14.992	15.006	15.046	15.096	14.910	14.938	14.860	14.900	14.994	15.074	15.074

Humidity (RH)	%	Data	91.500	90.880	90.440	91.310	90.750	90.500	92.250	90.560	90.440	90.250	90.690	91.500
$E_d = e_a \times RH$		Hitungan	24.280	23.938	23.922	24.463	24.699	23.281	23.925	22.957	23.198	23.785	24.513	24.732
$e_d = e_a - E_d$		Hitungan	2.256	2.402	2.529	2.328	2.517	2.444	2.010	2.393	2.452	2.570	2.516	2.297
Square		Hitungan	1.502	1.550	1.590	1.526	1.587	1.563	1.418	1.547	1.566	1.603	1.586	1.516
$F(e_d) = 0.34 - 0.044 \text{ square } e_d$		Hitungan	0.274	0.272	0.270	0.273	0.270	0.271	0.278	0.272	0.271	0.269	0.270	0.273
Ra	mm/day	Tabel	15.150	15.600	15.700	15.200	14.250	13.700	13.900	14.650	15.250	15.450	15.200	14.950
Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.480	0.460	0.510	0.490	0.520	0.460	0.460	0.450	0.460	0.450	0.470	0.500
$R_s = (0.25 + 0.54 \text{ n/N}) \cdot R_a$		Hitungan	7.714	7.775	8.249	7.822	7.564	6.828	6.928	7.222	7.601	7.617	7.658	7.774
$R_{ns} = (1-a)R_s, a=0.25$		Hitungan	5.786	5.831	6.187	5.866	5.673	5.121	5.196	5.417	5.700	5.713	5.743	5.831
$F(n/N) = 0.1 + 0.9 \text{ n/N}$	%	Hitungan	0.532	0.514	0.559	0.541	0.568	0.514	0.514	0.505	0.514	0.505	0.523	0.550
Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.740	0.810	0.950	0.820	0.840	0.930	0.770	0.810	0.910	0.910	0.820	0.890
$F(u) = 0.27(1 + (u \times 0.864))$		Hitungan	0.443	0.459	0.492	0.461	0.466	0.487	0.450	0.459	0.482	0.482	0.461	0.478
$R_{n1} = f(t) \cdot f(e_d) \cdot f(n/N)$		Hitungan	2.188	2.094	2.265	2.221	2.317	2.079	2.132	2.041	2.076	2.040	2.130	2.266
$R_n = R_{ns} - R_{n1}$	mm/day	Hitungan	3.598	3.737	3.921	3.645	3.356	3.043	3.064	3.376	3.624	3.672	3.613	3.565
Correction figure (c)		Data	1.100	1.100	1.000	1.000	0.950	0.950	1.000	1.000	1.100	1.100	1.150	1.150
Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	2.852	2.978	3.152	2.911	2.739	2.501	2.436	2.705	2.910	2.972	2.917	2.864
$E_{t0} = c \times E_{to}^*$	mm/day	Hitungan	3.137	3.276	3.152	2.911	2.602	2.376	2.436	2.705	3.201	3.269	3.354	3.293
Number of days in one month	Day	Hitungan	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Eto	mm/bulan	Hitungan	97.249	91.718	97.703	87.344	80.651	71.285	75.514	83.851	96.015	101.330	100.625	102.097

Varibale	Unit	exp	Evapotranspiration 2019											
			JAN	FEB	Maret	APR	MEI	JUN	JUL	AGU	SEP	OKT	NOV	DES
Temperature (T)	oC	Data	22.210	22.270	22.150	22.620	22.600	22.120	21.320	21.480	21.680	22.100	22.250	22.600
Ea (ea)	mbar	Tabel	26.757	26.859	26.655	27.454	27.420	26.604	25.380	25.620	25.920	26.570	26.825	27.420
W		Tabel	0.714	0.715	0.714	0.719	0.718	0.714	0.706	0.707	0.709	0.713	0.715	0.718
1-W		Hitungan	0.286	0.285	0.286	0.282	0.282	0.287	0.295	0.293	0.291	0.287	0.285	0.282
f(T)		Tabel	15.042	15.054	15.030	15.124	15.120	15.024	14.864	14.896	14.936	15.020	15.050	15.120
Humidity (RH)	%	Data	91.440	91.620	90.560	91.560	92.380	92.310	91.690	90.560	88.940	90.190	89.250	90.380
$E_d = e_a \times RH$		Hitungan	24.467	24.608	24.139	25.137	25.331	24.558	23.271	23.201	23.053	23.963	23.941	24.782
$e_d = e_a - E_d$		Hitungan	2.290	2.251	2.516	2.317	2.089	2.046	2.109	2.419	2.867	2.607	2.884	2.638
Square		Hitungan	1.513	1.500	1.586	1.522	1.445	1.430	1.452	1.555	1.693	1.614	1.698	1.624

$F(ed) = 0.34 - 0.044 \text{ sqaue ed}$		Hitungan	0.273	0.274	0.270	0.273	0.276	0.277	0.276	0.272	0.266	0.269	0.265	0.269
Ra	mm/day	Tabel	15.150	15.600	15.700	15.200	14.250	13.700	13.900	14.650	15.250	15.450	15.200	14.950
Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.520	0.480	0.550	0.480	0.500	0.410	0.430	0.410	0.460	0.470	0.540	0.520
$R_s = (0.25 + 0.54 \text{ n/N}) \cdot R_a$		Hitungan	8.042	7.944	8.588	7.740	7.410	6.458	6.703	6.906	7.601	7.784	8.232	7.935
$R_{ns} = (1-a)R_s, a=0.25$		Hitungan	6.031	5.958	6.441	5.805	5.558	4.844	5.027	5.180	5.700	5.838	6.174	5.952
$F(n/N) = 0.1 + 0.9 \text{ n/N}$	%	Hitungan	0.568	0.532	0.595	0.532	0.550	0.469	0.487	0.469	0.514	0.523	0.586	0.568
Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.820	0.680	0.750	0.730	0.700	0.920	0.890	0.940	0.940	0.730	0.880	0.780
$F(u) = 0.27(1 + (u \times 0.864))$		Hitungan	0.461	0.429	0.445	0.440	0.433	0.485	0.478	0.489	0.489	0.440	0.475	0.452
$R_{n1} = f(t) \cdot f(ed) \cdot f(n/N)$		Hitungan	2.336	2.194	2.416	2.197	2.299	1.952	1.999	1.897	2.038	2.113	2.340	2.306
$R_n = R_{ns} - R_{n1}$	mm/day	Hitungan	3.695	3.763	4.025	3.608	3.259	2.891	3.028	3.282	3.662	3.725	3.835	3.645
Correction figure (c)		Data	1.100	1.100	1.000	1.000	0.950	0.950	1.000	1.000	1.100	1.100	1.150	1.150
Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	2.942	2.966	3.193	2.880	2.596	2.347	2.433	2.667	3.005	2.986	3.132	2.954
$E_{t0} = c \times E_{to}^*$	mm/day	Hitungan	3.236	3.262	3.193	2.880	2.466	2.230	2.433	2.667	3.305	3.285	3.602	3.397
Number of days in one month	Day	Hitungan	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Eto	mm/bulan	Hitungan	100.309	91.345	98.987	86.389	76.451	66.891	75.427	82.692	99.161	101.824	108.050	105.320

Varibale	Unit	exp	Evapotranspiration 2020											
			JAN	FEB	Maret	APR	MEI	JUN	JUL	AGU	SEP	OKT	NOV	DES
Temperature (T)	oC	Data	22.830	22.870	22.470	22.480	22.760	22.130	21.740	21.810	22.120	22.010	22.210	22.110
Ea (ea)	mbar	Tabel	27.811	27.879	27.199	27.216	27.692	26.621	26.010	26.115	26.604	26.417	26.757	26.587
W		Tabel	0.721	0.721	0.717	0.717	0.720	0.714	0.710	0.710	0.714	0.712	0.714	0.713
1-W		Hitungan	0.279	0.279	0.283	0.283	0.280	0.286	0.290	0.290	0.287	0.288	0.286	0.287
f(T)		Tabel	15.166	15.174	15.094	15.096	15.152	15.026	14.948	14.962	15.024	15.002	15.042	15.022
Humidity (RH)	%	Data	89.880	90.380	91.750	91.810	91.120	91.120	89.880	90.310	89.500	89.810	91.380	91.880
$E_d = e_a \times RH$		Hitungan	24.997	25.197	24.955	24.987	25.233	24.257	23.378	23.584	23.811	23.725	24.451	24.428
$e_d = e_a - E_d$		Hitungan	2.814	2.682	2.244	2.229	2.459	2.364	2.632	2.531	2.793	2.692	2.306	2.159
Square		Hitungan	1.678	1.638	1.498	1.493	1.568	1.538	1.622	1.591	1.671	1.641	1.519	1.469
$F(ed) = 0.34 - 0.044 \text{ sqaue ed}$		Hitungan	0.266	0.268	0.274	0.274	0.271	0.272	0.269	0.270	0.266	0.268	0.273	0.275
Ra	mm/day	Tabel	15.150	15.600	15.700	15.200	14.250	13.700	13.900	14.650	15.250	15.450	15.200	14.950
Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.550	0.530	0.510	0.540	0.510	0.480	0.460	0.450	0.450	0.470	0.480	0.480
$R_s = (0.25 + 0.54 \text{ n/N}) \cdot R_a$		Hitungan	8.287	8.365	8.249	8.232	7.487	6.976	6.928	7.222	7.518	7.784	7.740	7.613

$R_{ns} = (1-a)R_s$, $a=0.25$		Hitungan	6.215	6.274	6.187	6.174	5.615	5.232	5.196	5.417	5.639	5.838	5.805	5.709
$F(n/N) = 0.1+0.9 n/N$	%	Hitungan	0.595	0.577	0.559	0.586	0.559	0.532	0.514	0.505	0.505	0.523	0.532	0.532
Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.730	0.620	0.670	0.630	0.930	0.890	0.960	0.880	0.900	0.880	0.920	0.700
$F(u) = 0.27(1+(u_x0.864))$		Hitungan	0.440	0.415	0.426	0.417	0.487	0.478	0.494	0.475	0.480	0.475	0.485	0.433
$R_{n1}=f(t).f(ed).f(n/N)$		Hitungan	2.402	2.346	2.313	2.427	2.295	2.177	2.064	2.040	2.022	2.101	2.186	2.201
$R_n = R_{ns} - R_{n1}$	mm/day	Hitungan	3.813	3.928	3.874	3.748	3.320	3.055	3.132	3.377	3.617	3.737	3.619	3.509
Correction figure (c)		Data	1.100	1.100	1.000	1.000	0.950	0.950	1.000	1.000	1.100	1.100	1.150	1.150
Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	3.094	3.142	3.048	2.950	2.725	2.503	2.600	2.747	2.965	3.030	2.905	2.771
$E_{t0} = c \times E_{to}^*$	mm/day	Hitungan	3.404	3.456	3.048	2.950	2.589	2.378	2.600	2.747	3.261	3.333	3.340	3.187
Number of days in one month	Day	Hitungan	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Eto	mm/bulan	Hitungan	105.509	96.775	94.498	88.511	80.262	71.346	80.607	85.161	97.840	103.319	100.206	98.798

Varibale	Unit	exp	Evapotranspiration 2021											
			JAN	FEB	Maret	APR	MEI	JUN	JUL	AGU	SEP	OKT	NOV	DES
Temperature (T)	oC	Data	22.250	21.790	22.030	21.880	22.410	21.690	21.800	21.800	21.880	22.300	22.250	22.080
Ea (ea)	mbar	Tabel	26.825	26.085	26.451	26.220	27.097	25.935	26.100	26.100	26.220	26.910	26.825	26.536
W		Tabel	0.715	0.710	0.713	0.711	0.716	0.709	0.710	0.710	0.711	0.715	0.715	0.713
1-W		Hitungan	0.285	0.290	0.287	0.289	0.284	0.291	0.290	0.290	0.289	0.285	0.285	0.287
f(T)		Tabel	15.050	14.958	15.006	14.976	15.082	14.938	14.960	14.960	14.976	15.060	15.050	15.016
Humidity (RH)	%	Data	91.560	90.750	90.810	91.310	92.120	91.940	91.620	91.250	90.880	91.000	90.440	91.440
$E_d = e_a \times RH$		Hitungan	24.561	23.672	24.020	23.941	24.962	23.845	23.913	23.816	23.829	24.488	24.261	24.265
$e_d = e_a - E_d$		Hitungan	2.264	2.413	2.431	2.279	2.135	2.090	2.187	2.284	2.391	2.422	2.564	2.271
Square		Hitungan	1.505	1.553	1.559	1.509	1.461	1.446	1.479	1.511	1.546	1.556	1.601	1.507
$F(ed) = 0.34 - 0.044 \text{ square } e_d$		Hitungan	0.274	0.272	0.271	0.274	0.276	0.276	0.275	0.274	0.272	0.272	0.270	0.274
Ra	mm/day	Tabel	15.150	15.600	15.700	15.200	14.250	13.700	13.900	14.650	15.250	15.450	15.200	14.950
Sun exposure, n/N	%	Data	0.460	0.450	0.480	0.480	0.500	0.470	0.460	0.470	0.430	0.480	0.480	0.450
$R_s=(0.25+0.54 n/N).R_a$		Hitungan	7.551	7.691	7.994	7.740	7.410	6.902	6.928	7.381	7.354	7.867	7.740	7.370
$R_{ns} = (1-a)R_s$, $a=0.25$		Hitungan	5.663	5.768	5.996	5.805	5.558	5.177	5.196	5.536	5.515	5.900	5.805	5.528
$F(n/N) = 0.1+0.9 n/N$	%	Hitungan	0.514	0.505	0.532	0.532	0.550	0.523	0.514	0.523	0.487	0.532	0.532	0.505
Wind speed, U	m/s	Data	0.740	0.900	0.620	0.910	0.980	0.900	0.830	0.900	0.890	0.840	0.940	0.950
$F(u) = 0.27(1+(u_x0.864))$		Hitungan	0.443	0.480	0.415	0.482	0.499	0.480	0.464	0.480	0.478	0.466	0.489	0.492

$Rn1=f(t).f(ed).f(n/N)$		Hitungan	2.118	2.052	2.167	2.180	2.287	2.159	2.114	2.140	1.983	2.175	2.158	2.075
$Rn = Rns - Rn1$	mm/day	Hitungan	3.545	3.716	3.829	3.625	3.270	3.017	3.082	3.396	3.532	3.725	3.647	3.452
Correction figure (c)		Data	1.100	1.100	1.000	1.000	0.950	0.950	1.000	1.000	1.100	1.100	1.150	1.150
Eto*	mm/day	Hitungan	2.820	2.975	3.018	2.895	2.645	2.432	2.483	2.729	2.841	2.986	2.965	2.782
$Et0 = c \times Eto^*$	mm/day	Hitungan	3.102	3.272	3.018	2.895	2.513	2.310	2.483	2.729	3.125	3.284	3.409	3.200
Number of days in one month	Day	Hitungan	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Eto	mm/bulan	Hitungan	96.156	91.623	93.569	86.860	77.893	69.301	76.965	84.612	93.764	101.813	102.278	99.188

Varibale	Unit	Expl	Monthly Dependable Discharge (2012)											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Agust	Sept	Okt	Nov	Des
Meteorological data														
Rainy Month (R)	mm/month	data	202.740	256.090	441.000	184.320	447.310	333.740	153.510	157.240	163.220	100.980	231.270	183.620
Number of rainy days (n)	Day	data	16.000	15.000	20.000	14.000	24.000	19.000	10.000	9.000	12.000	7.000	11.000	10.000
Evaporasi Aktual (Ea)														
Evaporasi Potensial (Eto)	mm/month	data	99.142	94.872	92.156	86.547	76.144	66.086	75.274	80.295	94.688	106.466	96.585	99.508
Permukaan Lahan yang terbuka (m)	%	Asum.	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
$Eto/Ea = M/20 \times (18-n)$	%	Cal	0.010	0.015	-0.010	0.020	-0.030	-0.005	0.040	0.045	0.030	0.055	0.035	0.040
$Ee=Eto \times (m/20) \times (18-n)$	mm/month	Cal	0.991	1.423	-0.922	1.731	-2.284	-0.330	3.011	3.613	2.841	5.856	3.380	3.980
$Ea=Eto - Ee$	mm/month	Cal	98.151	93.449	93.078	84.816	78.428	66.417	72.263	76.682	91.848	100.610	93.205	95.528
Water Balanced														
$\Delta s = R - Ea$	mm/month	Cal	104.589	162.641	347.922	99.504	368.882	267.323	81.247	80.558	71.372	0.370	138.065	88.092
Limpasan badai (PF=)		Conts	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ground water content (SS)	mm/month	(8) - (9)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Soil moisture capacity	mm/month	Cal	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000
Kelebihan Air (WS= $\Delta S - SS$)	mm/month	Cal	104.589	162.641	347.922	99.504	368.882	267.323	81.247	80.558	71.372	0.370	138.065	88.092
Runoff and storage ground water														
Factor i	0.4	Conts	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400
factor k	0.6	Conts	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600
Infiltration ($I= i \times WS$)	mm/month	Cal	41.836	65.056	139.169	39.802	147.553	106.929	32.499	32.223	28.549	0.148	55.226	35.237

Ground water volume $G=0,5(I+k) \cdot I$		Cal	33.469	52.045	111.335	31.841	118.042	85.543	25.999	25.779	22.839	0.118	44.181	28.190
Vn-1			100.000	93.469	108.126	176.211	137.568	200.583	205.893	149.535	115.500	92.139	55.402	77.422
$L = k \cdot (Vn - I)$		Cal	60.000	56.081	64.876	105.727	82.541	120.350	123.536	89.721	69.300	55.283	33.241	46.453
Storage vol (Vn)		Cal	93.469	108.126	176.211	137.568	200.583	205.893	149.535	115.500	92.139	55.402	77.422	74.643
$Dvn=Vn-Vn-I$		Cal	-6.531	14.658	68.085	-38.643	63.015	5.310	-56.358	-34.035	-23.361	-36.737	22.020	-2.779
Base flow (BF)	mm/month	Cal	48.367	50.399	71.084	78.445	84.538	101.619	88.857	66.259	51.910	36.885	33.206	38.016
Direct Runoff (DR)	mm/month	Cal	62.754	97.585	208.753	59.702	221.329	160.394	48.748	48.335	42.823	0.222	82.839	52.855
Total runoff (Tro)	mm/month	Cal	111.121	147.983	279.838	138.147	305.867	262.013	137.605	114.593	94.733	37.107	116.045	90.872
Capture area	km2	Data	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172
Number of rain in obe month	Day	data	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Monthly Discharge	m3/s	Cal	11.333	16.710	28.541	14.559	31.196	27.614	14.034	11.687	9.984	3.785	12.230	9.268

Varibale	Unit	Expl	Monthly Dependable Discharge (2013)											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Agust	Sept	Okt	Nov	Des
Meteorological data														
Rainy Month (R)	mm/month	data	452.350	487.350	428.650	319.560	175.630	153.370	245.690	308.030	119.670	142.760	245.760	270.610
Number of rainy days (n)	Day	data	15.000	14.000	18.000	16.000	12.000	11.000	17.000	14.000	3.000	8.000	12.000	17.000
Evaporasi Aktual (Ea)														
Evaporasi Potensial (Eto)	mm/month	data	97.586	91.894	97.189	85.090	77.846	68.028	73.241	81.972	95.325	101.183	96.306	97.031
Permukaan Lahan yang terbuka (m)	%	Asum.	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
$Eto/Ea = M/20 \times (18-n)$	%	Cal	0.015	0.020	0.000	0.010	0.030	0.035	0.005	0.020	0.075	0.050	0.030	0.005
$Ee=Eto \times (m/20) \times (18-n)$	mm/month	Cal	1.464	1.838	0.000	0.851	2.335	2.381	0.366	1.639	7.149	5.059	2.889	0.485
$Ea=Eto - Ee$	mm/month	Cal	96.122	90.056	97.189	84.239	75.511	65.647	72.875	80.332	88.176	96.124	93.417	96.546
Water Balanced														
$\Delta s = R - Ea$	mm/month	Cal	356.228	397.294	331.461	235.321	100.119	87.723	172.815	227.698	31.494	46.636	152.343	174.064
Limpasan badai (PF=)		Conts	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ground water content (SS)	mm/month	(8) - (9)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Soil moisture capacity	mm/month	Cal	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000
Kelebihan Air (WS= $\Delta S - SS$)	mm/month	Cal	356.228	397.294	331.461	235.321	100.119	87.723	172.815	227.698	31.494	46.636	152.343	174.064

Runoff and storage ground water														
Factor i	0.4	Conts	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400
factor k	0.6	Conts	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600
Infiltration (I= i x WS)	mm/month	Cal	142.491	158.918	132.584	94.128	40.048	35.089	69.126	91.079	12.598	18.654	60.937	69.626
Ground water volume G=0,5(I+k). I		Cal	113.993	127.134	106.068	75.303	32.038	28.071	55.301	72.863	10.078	14.923	48.750	55.701
Vn-1			74.643	158.778	222.401	239.508	219.008	163.443	126.137	130.983	151.453	100.950	75.493	94.046
L = k. (Vn - I)		Cal	44.786	95.267	133.441	143.705	131.405	98.066	75.682	78.590	90.872	60.570	45.296	56.428
Storage vol (Vn)		Cal	158.778	222.401	239.508	219.008	163.443	126.137	130.983	151.453	100.950	75.493	94.046	112.128
Dvn=Vn-Vn-I		Cal	84.136	63.623	17.107	-20.501	-55.565	-37.306	4.846	20.470	-50.503	-25.456	18.553	18.082
Base flow (BF)	mm/month	Cal	58.355	95.295	115.477	114.629	95.613	72.395	64.280	70.609	63.101	44.111	42.385	51.544
Direct Runoff (DR)	mm/month	Cal	213.737	238.376	198.877	141.193	60.071	52.634	103.689	136.619	18.896	27.982	91.406	104.439
Total runoff (Tro)	mm/month	Cal	272.092	333.671	314.354	255.822	155.684	125.028	167.969	207.227	81.997	72.092	133.791	155.982
Capture area	km2	Data	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172
Number of rain in obe month	Day	data	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Monthly Discharge	m3/s	Cal	27.751	37.678	32.061	26.961	15.878	13.177	17.131	21.135	8.642	7.353	14.100	15.909

Varibale	Unit	Expl	Monthly Dependable Discharge (2014)											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Agust	Sept	Okt	Nov	Des
meteorological data														
Rainy Month (R)	mm/month	data	311.370	123.950	436.040	305.520	276.330	128.320	243.950	213.320	224.610	71.290	182.620	343.550
Number of rainy days (n)	Day	data	14.000	6.000	16.000	16.000	17.000	11.000	7.000	13.000	13.000	6.000	11.000	13.000
Evaporasi Aktual (Ea)														
Evaporasi Potensial (Eto)	mm/month	data	100.808	98.317	95.358	88.621	78.932	69.325	77.566	81.403	94.767	108.413	100.680	95.995
Permukaan Lahan yang terbuka (m)	%	Asum.	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
Eto/Ea = M/20 x (18-n)	%	Cal	0.020	0.060	0.010	0.010	0.005	0.035	0.055	0.025	0.025	0.060	0.035	0.025
Ee=Eto x (m/20) x (18-n)	mm/month	Cal	2.016	5.899	0.954	0.886	0.395	2.426	4.266	2.035	2.369	6.505	3.524	2.400
Ea=Eto - Ee	mm/month	Cal	98.792	92.418	94.405	87.735	78.537	66.898	73.300	79.368	92.398	101.909	97.156	93.595
Water Balanced														
$\Delta s = R - Ea$	mm/month	Cal	212.578	31.532	341.635	217.785	197.793	61.422	170.650	133.952	132.212	-30.619	85.464	249.955
Limpasan badai (PF=)		Conts	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	3.565	0.000	0.000

Ground water content (SS)	mm/month	(8) - (9)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-34.183	0.000	0.000
Soil moisture capacity	mm/month	Cal	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	-34.183	200.000	200.000
Kelebihan Air (WS=ΔS - SS)	mm/month	Cal	212.578	31.532	341.635	217.785	197.793	61.422	170.650	133.952	132.212	3.565	85.464	249.955
Runoff and storage ground water														
Factor i	0.4	Conts	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400
factor k	0.6	Conts	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600
Infiltration (I= i x WS)	mm/month	Cal	85.031	12.613	136.654	87.114	79.117	24.569	68.260	53.581	52.885	1.426	34.185	99.982
Ground water volume $G=0,5(I+k) \cdot I$		Cal	68.025	10.090	109.323	69.691	63.294	19.655	54.608	42.865	42.308	1.141	27.348	79.985
Vn-1			112.128	135.302	91.271	164.086	168.143	164.179	118.163	125.505	118.168	113.209	69.066	68.788
L = k. (Vn - I)		Cal	67.277	81.181	54.763	98.452	100.886	98.508	70.898	75.303	70.901	67.925	41.440	41.273
Storage vol (Vn)		Cal	135.302	91.271	164.086	168.143	164.179	118.163	125.505	118.168	113.209	69.066	68.788	121.258
Dvn=Vn-Vn-I		Cal	23.174	-44.030	72.815	4.057	-3.963	-46.017	7.343	-7.338	-4.959	-44.143	-0.278	52.470
Base flow (BF)	mm/month	Cal	61.857	56.643	63.839	83.057	83.081	70.585	60.917	60.918	57.844	45.569	34.463	47.512
Direct Runoff (DR)	mm/month	Cal	127.547	18.919	204.981	130.671	118.676	36.853	102.390	80.371	79.327	5.703	51.278	149.973
Total runoff (Tro)	mm/month	Cal	189.404	75.563	268.821	213.728	201.756	107.438	163.307	141.289	137.172	51.272	85.742	197.484
Capture area	km2	Data	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172
Number of rain in obe month	Day	data	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Monthly Discharge	m3/s	Cal	19.317	8.532	27.417	22.525	20.577	11.323	16.656	14.410	14.457	5.229	9.036	20.142

Varibale	Unit	Expl	Monthly Dependable Discharge (2015)											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Agust	Sept	Okt	Nov	Des
Meteorological data														
Rainy Month (R)	mm/month	data	209.090	412.570	444.300	614.690	195.090	209.450	55.980	52.990	49.800	64.640	85.580	591.470
Number of rainy days (n)	Day	data	15.000	18.000	19.000	24.000	11.000	12.000	2.000	2.000	3.000	4.000	6.000	21.000
Evaporasi Aktual (Ea)														
Evaporasi Potensial (Eto)	mm/month	data	99.760	94.046	95.500	88.545	78.668	70.210	82.864	89.056	103.607	114.496	98.745	104.734
Permukaan Lahan yang terbuka (m)	%	Asum.	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
Eto/Ea = M/20 x (18-n)	%	Cal	0.015	0.000	-0.005	-0.030	0.035	0.030	0.080	0.080	0.075	0.070	0.060	-0.015
Ee=Eto x (m/20) x (18-n)	mm/month	Cal	1.496	0.000	-0.477	-2.656	2.753	2.106	6.629	7.124	7.771	8.015	5.925	-1.571
Ea=Eto - Ee	mm/month	Cal	98.263	94.046	95.977	91.201	75.915	68.104	76.235	81.932	95.836	106.481	92.821	106.305

Eto/Ea = M/20 x (18-n)	%	Cal	0.000	0.005	0.000	0.000	0.050	0.030	-0.015	0.040	0.040	0.030	0.020	-0.005
Ee=Eto x (m/20) x (18-n)	mm/month	Cal	0.000	0.464	0.000	0.000	3.926	2.027	-1.107	3.504	3.766	2.922	1.996	-0.497
Ea=Eto - Ee	mm/month	Cal	94.838	92.406	89.808	87.184	74.597	65.555	74.895	84.099	90.389	94.467	97.811	99.904
Water Balanced														
$\Delta s = R - E_a$	mm/month	Cal	343.062	273.774	253.112	357.266	146.513	147.995	372.215	67.961	95.851	73.033	113.079	192.146
Limpasan badai (PF=)		Conts	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ground water content (SS)	mm/month	(8) - (9)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Soil moisture capacity	mm/month	Cal	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000
Kelebihan Air (WS= $\Delta S - SS$)	mm/month	Cal	343.062	273.774	253.112	357.266	146.513	147.995	372.215	67.961	95.851	73.033	113.079	192.146
Runoff and storage ground water														
Factor i	0.4	Conts	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400
factor k	0.6	Conts	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600
Infiltration (I= i x WS)	mm/month	Cal	137.225	109.510	101.245	142.907	58.605	59.198	148.886	27.184	38.340	29.213	45.231	76.858
Ground water volume G=0,5(I+k). I		Cal	109.780	87.608	80.996	114.325	46.884	47.358	119.109	21.747	30.672	23.371	36.185	61.487
Vn-1			164.922	208.733	212.848	208.704	239.548	190.613	161.726	216.144	151.434	121.533	96.290	93.959
L = k. (Vn - I)		Cal	98.953	125.240	127.709	125.223	143.729	114.368	97.036	129.687	90.860	72.920	57.774	56.376
Storage vol (Vn)		Cal	208.733	212.848	208.704	239.548	190.613	161.726	216.144	151.434	121.533	96.290	93.959	117.862
Dvn=Vn-Vn-I		Cal	43.811	4.115	-4.143	30.844	-48.935	-28.887	54.418	-64.710	-29.901	-25.242	-2.331	23.903
Base flow (BF)	mm/month	Cal	93.414	105.395	105.388	112.063	107.540	88.085	94.468	91.895	68.242	54.456	47.562	52.955
Direct Runoff (DR)	mm/month	Cal	205.837	164.265	151.867	214.360	87.908	88.797	223.329	40.776	57.510	43.820	67.847	115.288
Total runoff (Tro)	mm/month	Cal	299.251	269.660	257.255	326.423	195.448	176.882	317.796	132.671	125.752	98.276	115.410	168.243
Capture area	km2	Data	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172
Number of rain in obe month	Day	data	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Monthly Discharge	m3/s	Cal	30.521	30.449	26.238	34.402	19.934	18.642	32.412	13.531	13.253	10.023	12.163	17.159

Varibale	Unit	Expl	Monthly Dependable Discharge (2017)											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Agust	Sept	Okt	Nov	Des
Meteorological data														
Rainy Month (R)	mm/month	data	251.740	393.380	426.850	592.950	264.930	254.460	308.670	190.200	217.150	220.370	187.990	291.170
Number of rainy days (n)	Day	data	18.000	22.000	21.000	24.000	16.000	14.000	14.000	12.000	13.000	8.000	10.000	16.000

Evaporasi Aktual (Ea)														
Evaporasi Potensial (Eto)	mm/month	data	97.312	91.957	92.353	85.072	75.834	67.626	74.567	81.809	95.389	104.077	96.900	101.204
Permukaan Lahan yang terbuka (m)	%	Asum.	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
Eto/Ea = M/20 x (18-n)	%	Cal	0.000	-0.020	-0.015	-0.030	0.010	0.020	0.020	0.030	0.025	0.050	0.040	0.010
Ee=Eto x (m/20) x (18-n)	mm/month	Cal	0.000	-1.839	-1.385	-2.552	0.758	1.353	1.491	2.454	2.385	5.204	3.876	1.012
Ea=Eto - Ee	mm/month	Cal	97.312	93.797	93.739	87.624	75.075	66.274	73.075	79.355	93.004	98.873	93.024	100.192
Water Balanced														
$\Delta s = R - Ea$	mm/month	Cal	154.428	299.583	333.111	505.326	189.855	188.186	235.595	110.845	124.146	121.497	94.966	190.978
Limpasan badai (PF=)		Conts	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ground water content (SS)	mm/month	(8) - (9)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Soil moisture capacity	mm/month	Cal	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000
Kelebihan Air (WS= $\Delta S - SS$)	mm/month	Cal	154.428	299.583	333.111	505.326	189.855	188.186	235.595	110.845	124.146	121.497	94.966	190.978
Runoff and storage ground water														
Factor i	0.4	Conts	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400
factor k	0.6	Conts	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600
Infiltration (I= i x WS)	mm/month	Cal	61.771	119.833	133.245	202.130	75.942	75.274	94.238	44.338	49.658	48.599	37.986	76.391
Ground water volume $G=0,5(I+k). I$		Cal	49.417	95.867	106.596	161.704	60.753	60.220	75.390	35.470	39.727	38.879	30.389	61.113
Vn-1			117.862	120.134	167.947	207.364	286.123	232.427	199.676	195.196	152.588	131.280	117.647	100.977
$L = k. (Vn - I)$		Cal	70.717	72.081	100.768	124.418	171.674	139.456	119.806	117.118	91.553	78.768	70.588	60.586
Storage vol (Vn)		Cal	120.134	167.947	207.364	286.123	232.427	199.676	195.196	152.588	131.280	117.647	100.977	121.699
Dvn= $Vn - Vn - I$		Cal	2.272	47.813	39.417	78.759	-53.696	-32.751	-4.480	-42.608	-21.308	-13.633	-16.670	20.722
Base flow (BF)	mm/month	Cal	59.499	72.020	93.828	123.372	129.637	108.026	98.718	86.946	70.967	62.232	54.656	55.669
Direct Runoff (DR)	mm/month	Cal	92.657	179.750	199.867	303.196	113.913	112.912	141.357	66.507	74.488	72.898	56.979	114.587
Total runoff (Tro)	mm/month	Cal	152.156	251.770	293.695	426.567	243.550	220.937	240.075	153.453	145.455	135.130	111.635	170.256
Capture area	km2	Data	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172
Number of rain in obe month	Day	data	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Monthly Discharge	m3/s	Cal	15.518	28.429	29.954	44.956	24.840	23.285	24.485	15.651	15.329	13.782	11.765	17.364

Number of rain in obe month	Day	data	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Monthly Discharge	m3/s	Cal	13.238	27.154	31.371	18.958	11.306	11.070	13.881	5.997	4.579	4.855	21.553	23.360

Varibale	Unit	Expl	Monthly Dependable Discharge (2019)											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Agust	Sept	Okt	Nov	Des
Meteorological data														
Rainy Month (R)	mm/month	data	485.300	478.500	331.680	361.530	265.480	299.630	145.100	108.680	73.160	126.520	88.870	279.180
Number of rainy days (n)	Day	data	23.000	17.000	17.000	13.000	16.000	16.000	11.000	7.000	4.000	11.000	7.000	11.000
Evaporasi Aktual (Ea)														
Evaporasi Potensial (Eto)	mm/month	data	100.309	91.345	98.987	86.389	76.451	66.891	75.427	82.692	99.161	101.824	108.050	105.320
Permukaan Lahan yang terbuka (m)	%	Asum.	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
Eto/Ea = M/20 x (18-n)	%	Cal	-0.025	0.005	0.005	0.025	0.010	0.010	0.035	0.055	0.070	0.035	0.055	0.035
Ee=Eto x (m/20) x (18-n)	mm/month	Cal	-2.508	0.457	0.495	2.160	0.765	0.669	2.640	4.548	6.941	3.564	5.943	3.686
Ea=Eto - Ee	mm/month	Cal	102.817	90.888	98.493	84.230	75.686	66.222	72.787	78.144	92.220	98.260	102.107	101.634
Water Balanced														
$\Delta s = R - Ea$	mm/month	Cal	382.483	387.612	233.187	277.300	189.794	233.408	72.313	30.536	-19.060	28.260	-13.237	177.546
Limpasan badai (PF=)		Conts	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	3.658	0.000	4.444	0.000
Ground water content (SS)	mm/month	(8) - (9)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-22.718	0.000	-17.681	0.000
Soil moisture capacity	mm/month	Cal	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	-22.718	200.000	-17.681	200.000
Kelebihan Air (WS= $\Delta S - SS$)	mm/month	Cal	382.483	387.612	233.187	277.300	189.794	233.408	72.313	30.536	3.658	28.260	4.444	177.546
Runoff and storage ground water														
Factor i	0.4	Conts	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400
factor k	0.6	Conts	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600
Infiltration (I= i x WS)	mm/month	Cal	152.993	155.045	93.275	110.920	75.918	93.363	28.925	12.215	1.463	11.304	1.777	71.018
Ground water volume $G=0,5(I+k) \cdot I$		Cal	122.395	124.036	74.620	88.736	60.734	74.691	23.140	9.772	1.171	9.043	1.422	56.815
Vn-1			154.678	215.202	253.157	226.514	224.645	195.521	192.003	138.342	92.777	56.837	43.145	27.309
$L = k \cdot (Vn - I)$		Cal	92.807	129.121	151.894	135.908	134.787	117.312	115.202	83.005	55.666	34.102	25.887	16.385
Storage vol (Vn)		Cal	215.202	253.157	226.514	224.645	195.521	192.003	138.342	92.777	56.837	43.145	27.309	73.200
$Dvn=Vn-Vn-I$		Cal	60.523	37.955	-26.643	-1.869	-29.124	-3.518	-53.661	-45.565	-35.940	-13.691	-15.836	45.891
Base flow (BF)	mm/month	Cal	92.470	117.090	119.918	112.790	105.041	96.881	82.586	57.780	37.403	24.995	17.614	25.127

Direct Runoff (DR)	mm/month	Cal	229.490	232.567	139.912	166.380	113.876	140.045	43.388	18.322	5.853	16.956	7.110	106.527
Total runoff (Tro)	mm/month	Cal	321.960	349.657	259.830	279.170	218.918	236.926	125.974	76.102	43.256	41.951	24.723	131.655
Capture area	km2	Data	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172
Number of rain in obe month	Day	data	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Monthly Discharge	m3/s	Cal	32.837	39.483	26.500	29.422	22.328	24.970	12.848	7.762	4.559	4.279	2.606	13.428

Varibale	Unit	Expl	Monthly Dependable Discharge (2020)											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Agust	Sept	Okt	Nov	Des
Meteorological data														
Rainy Month (R)	mm/month	data	166.980	605.030	490.420	625.800	133.410	127.890	150.540	139.100	90.550	152.890	356.310	379.490
Number of rainy days (n)	Day	data	8.000	17.000	21.000	20.000	7.000	10.000	13.000	10.000	5.000	9.000	18.000	15.000
Evaporasi Aktual (Ea)														
Evaporasi Potensial (Eto)	mm/month	data	105.509	96.775	94.498	88.511	80.262	71.346	80.607	85.161	97.840	103.319	100.206	98.798
Permukaan Lahan yang terbuka (m)	%	Asum.	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
Eto/Ea = M/20 x (18-n)	%	Cal	0.050	0.005	-0.015	-0.010	0.055	0.040	0.025	0.040	0.065	0.045	0.000	0.015
Ee=Eto x (m/20) x (18-n)	mm/month	Cal	5.275	0.484	-1.417	-0.885	4.414	2.854	2.015	3.406	6.360	4.649	0.000	1.482
Ea=Eto - Ee	mm/month	Cal	100.233	96.291	95.916	89.396	75.847	68.492	78.591	81.755	91.481	98.669	100.206	97.316
Water Balanced														
$\Delta s = R - Ea$	mm/month	Cal	66.747	508.739	394.504	536.404	57.563	59.398	71.949	57.345	-0.931	54.221	256.104	282.174
Limpasan badai (PF=)		Conts	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	4.528	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ground water content (SS)	mm/month	(8) - (9)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-5.458	0.000	0.000	0.000
Soil moisture capacity	mm/month	Cal	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	-5.458	200.000	200.000	200.000
Kelebihan Air (WS= $\Delta S - SS$)	mm/month	Cal	66.747	508.739	394.504	536.404	57.563	59.398	71.949	57.345	4.528	54.221	256.104	282.174
Runoff and storage ground water														
Factor i	0.4	Conts	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400
factor k	0.6	Conts	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600
Infiltration (I= i x WS)	mm/month	Cal	26.699	203.495	157.802	214.562	23.025	23.759	28.779	22.938	1.811	21.688	102.442	112.870
Ground water volume G=0,5(I+k). I		Cal	21.359	162.796	126.241	171.649	18.420	19.007	23.024	18.350	1.449	17.351	81.953	90.296
Vn-1			73.200	65.279	201.964	247.420	320.101	210.481	145.296	110.201	84.471	52.131	48.630	111.131
L = k. (Vn - I)		Cal	43.920	39.167	121.178	148.452	192.061	126.288	87.178	66.121	50.683	31.279	29.178	66.679

Storage vol (Vn)		Cal	65.279	201.964	247.420	320.101	210.481	145.296	110.201	84.471	52.131	48.630	111.131	156.974
Dvn=Vn-Vn-I		Cal	-7.921	136.685	45.456	72.681	-109.620	-65.185	-35.095	-25.730	-32.340	-3.502	62.502	45.843
Base flow (BF)	mm/month	Cal	34.620	66.811	112.346	141.880	132.645	88.944	63.874	48.668	34.151	25.190	39.940	67.026
Direct Runoff (DR)	mm/month	Cal	40.048	305.243	236.703	321.842	34.538	35.639	43.169	34.407	7.244	32.532	153.663	169.304
Total runoff (Tro)	mm/month	Cal	74.668	372.054	349.048	463.723	167.183	124.583	107.043	83.075	41.395	57.723	193.603	236.331
Capture area	km2	Data	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172
Number of rain in obe month	Day	data	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Monthly Discharge	m3/s	Cal	7.615	42.012	35.600	48.872	17.051	13.130	10.917	8.473	4.363	5.887	20.404	24.104

Varibale	Unit	Expl	Monthly Dependable Discharge (2021)											
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Agust	Sept	Okt	Nov	Des
Meteorological data														
Rainy Month (R)	mm/month	data	137.980	494.820	214.950	477.860	334.910	167.800	206.950	268.380	241.740	97.750	117.730	378.400
Number of rainy days (n)	Day	data	11.000	18.000	14.000	20.000	18.000	15.000	12.000	15.000	13.000	10.000	7.000	20.000
Evaporasi Aktual (Ea)														
Evaporasi Potensial (Eto)	mm/month	data	96.156	91.623	93.569	86.860	77.893	69.301	76.965	84.612	93.764	101.813	102.278	99.188
Permukaan Lahan yang terbuka (m)	%	Asum.	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
Eto/Ea = M/20 x (18-n)	%	Cal	0.035	0.000	0.020	-0.010	0.000	0.015	0.030	0.015	0.025	0.040	0.055	-0.010
Ee=Eto x (m/20) x (18-n)	mm/month	Cal	3.365	0.000	1.871	-0.869	0.000	1.040	2.309	1.269	2.344	4.073	5.625	-0.992
Ea=Eto - Ee	mm/month	Cal	92.791	91.623	91.698	87.729	77.893	68.261	74.656	83.342	91.420	97.740	96.653	100.180
Water Balanced														
$\Delta s = R - Ea$	mm/month	Cal	45.189	403.197	123.252	390.131	257.017	99.539	132.294	185.038	150.320	0.010	21.077	278.220
Limpasan badai (PF=)		Conts	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ground water content (SS)	mm/month	(8) - (9)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Soil moisture capacity	mm/month	Cal	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000	200.000
Kelebihan Air (WS= $\Delta S - SS$)	mm/month	Cal	45.189	403.197	123.252	390.131	257.017	99.539	132.294	185.038	150.320	0.010	21.077	278.220
Runoff and storage ground water														
Factor i	0.4	Conts	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400	0.400
factor k	0.6	Conts	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600	0.600
Infiltration (I= i x WS)	mm/month	Cal	18.076	161.279	49.301	156.053	102.807	39.816	52.917	74.015	60.128	0.004	8.431	111.288

Ground water volume $G=0,5(I+k) \cdot I$		Cal	14.461	129.023	39.441	124.842	82.245	31.852	42.334	59.212	48.102	0.003	6.745	89.030
Vn-1			156.974	108.645	194.210	155.967	218.422	213.299	159.832	138.233	142.152	133.394	80.039	54.768
$L = k \cdot (Vn - I)$		Cal	94.185	65.187	116.526	93.580	131.053	127.979	95.899	82.940	85.291	80.036	48.024	32.861
Storage vol (Vn)		Cal	108.645	194.210	155.967	218.422	213.299	159.832	138.233	142.152	133.394	80.039	54.768	121.891
Dvn=Vn-Vn-I		Cal	-48.329	85.565	-38.243	62.455	-5.123	-53.467	-21.599	3.919	-8.758	-53.354	-25.271	67.123
Base flow (BF)	mm/month	Cal	66.405	75.714	87.544	93.597	107.930	93.283	74.516	70.096	68.886	53.358	33.702	44.165
Direct Runoff (DR)	mm/month	Cal	27.114	241.918	73.951	234.079	154.210	59.723	79.376	111.023	90.192	0.006	12.646	166.932
Total runoff (Tro)	mm/month	Cal	93.519	317.632	161.496	327.676	262.140	153.006	153.892	181.119	159.078	53.364	46.348	211.097
Capture area	km2	Data	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172	273.172
Number of rain in obe month	Day	data	31.000	28.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	31.000	30.000	31.000	30.000	31.000
Monthly Discharge	m3/s	Cal	9.538	35.866	16.471	34.534	26.736	16.125	15.696	18.472	16.765	5.443	4.885	21.530

Rekapitulation of Discharge

2012	11.33328	16.71002	28.5408	14.55935	31.19551	27.6136	14.03444	11.68746	9.983928	3.784566	12.22922	9.267894
2013	27.75072	37.6775	32.06111	26.96108	15.87828	13.17678	17.13125	21.13525	8.64169	7.352736	14.10025	15.90871
2014	19.31745	8.532402	27.41717	22.52487	20.57723	11.32297	16.65576	14.4102	14.45656	5.229246	9.036335	20.14153
2015	12.63312	29.34562	30.96466	46.43538	20.27823	19.18536	7.583005	4.752565	3.141735	2.154536	1.793687	34.30537
2016	30.52079	30.44948	26.23759	34.4018	19.93384	18.64162	32.41225	13.53121	13.25304	10.0232	12.16304	17.15921
2017	15.51847	28.42946	29.9541	44.95605	24.83983	23.28466	24.48537	15.65075	15.3295	13.78195	11.76527	17.36449
2018	13.23753	27.1544	31.3711	18.95775	11.3064	11.06975	13.88114	5.996515	4.578799	4.855474	21.55326	23.36001
2019	32.83686	39.48259	26.50023	29.42179	22.32754	24.96969	12.84816	7.761641	4.55878	4.278657	2.605581	13.42755
2020	7.615409	42.01164	35.59966	48.87186	17.05111	13.12985	10.91742	8.472891	4.362595	5.887171	20.40384	24.10351
2021	9.538007	35.86642	16.47102	34.53386	26.73585	16.12534	15.69557	18.47241	16.76532	5.44262	4.884647	21.5299
Average (2012-2021)	18.03016	29.56595	28.51174	32.16238	21.01238	17.85196	16.56444	12.18709	9.507194	6.279016	11.05351	19.65682

Other river data and analysis can be obtained by contacting author Elias Kondorrura Bawan.

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